
Series: PHYSICS

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Takeoff and fall of vector potential

Annotation

It is pointed out that the wave equation of electrodynamics contradicts the law of conservation of energy and therefore the solution of the system of Maxwell's equations must and can be replaced by another one in which this law is observed. This solution allows us to determine the vector potential, as a consequence of the system of Maxwell's equations. It turns out that, in the general case, the existence of a vector potential contradicts the system of Maxwell's equations. However, nevertheless, there is one case - an electromagnetic wave without longitudinal strengths. In this case, the vector potential exists and becomes proportional to the magnetic strength vector. The calibration of the vector potential, which introduces subjective arbitrariness into physics, becomes unnecessary.

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1. Introduction

Maxwell's system of equations is one of the best works of the human mind, and I want to justify this once again. I started with this phrase, because. from what follows, the reader may think that I want to prove otherwise and discard this paper. This system of equations has a generally

recognized solution - the [wave equation of electrodynamics](#), which makes a depressing impression: it [contradicts the law of conservation of energy](#) (LCE). This law is preserved on average, but is violated at every moment, which contradicts the very spirit of the LCE. There is no other branch of physics, except for electrodynamics, where they would be so calm about the violation of the LCE. It seems to me that this fact should be emphasized in all textbooks to call for a new solution. Indeed, the system of Maxwell's equations, as a system of differential equations with partial derivatives, has many mathematical solutions. But the wave equation is declared to be the only one on the basis of the fact that it satisfies the LCE on average!. This issue is considered in more detail in [1], where other shortcomings of the wave equation are also shown. I wrote about this to some authors of monographs on electrodynamics: proud silence was answer.

The solution, in which LCE is conserved, was found and published long ago in [2], but it did not receive the attention of official science. In [2], a solution was obtained in different coordinate systems and for various cases - for vacuum, capacitor, DC and AC wires, magnetic circuit, multi-phase machine, etc., i.e. for those cases that have so far been described by a subset of Maxwell's equations, and not by the whole system. Based on the new solution, the spiral structure of electromagnetic waves and stationary electromagnetic fields is theoretically predicted and experimentally confirmed, and it is also shown that spiral structures exist in all waves and technical devices without exception. For many experiments, explanations have been found that were previously absent.

All this allows me to repeat the initial phrase of admiration for Maxwell's system of equations and [use this as a criterion for the correctness of other achievements of electrodynamics](#).

2. Solution of Maxwell's equations for vacuum in the general case

Next, we consider Maxwell's equations for vacuum in the CGS system of the following form:

$$\operatorname{rot}(E) + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (a)$$

$$\operatorname{rot}(H) - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (b)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(E) = 0, \quad (c)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(H) = 0, \quad (d)$$

where H, E - magnetic and electrical strength, ε, μ - dielectric and magnetic permeability. In the system of cylindrical coordinate r, φ, z these equations have the form:

$$\frac{E_r}{r} + \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad \text{see (c)} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial z} = \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{dH_r}{dt}, \quad \text{see (a)} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial r} = \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{dH_\phi}{dt}, \quad \text{see (a)} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{E_\phi}{r} + \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{dH_z}{dt}, \quad \text{see (a)} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{H_r}{r} + \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad \text{see (d)} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial z} = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{dE_r}{dt}, \quad \text{see (b)} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial r} = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{dE_\phi}{dt}, \quad \text{see (b)} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{H_\phi}{r} + \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{dE_z}{dt}, \quad \text{see (b)} \quad (8)$$

where E_r, E_ϕ, E_z are electrical strengths, H_r, H_ϕ, H_z are magnetic strengths. The solution of system (1-8) has the following form:

$$H_r = h_r(r) \text{co}, \quad (9)$$

$$H_\phi = h_\phi(r) \text{si}, \quad (10)$$

$$H_z = h_z(r) \text{si}, \quad (11)$$

$$E_r = e_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (12)$$

$$E_\phi = e_\phi(r) \text{co}, \quad (13)$$

$$E_z = e_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (15)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (16)$$

where $h(r), e(r)$ are functions of the coordinate r and α, χ, ω are constants. The proof consists in substituting and differentiating expressions (9-16) into (1-8). For example, the divergence equation (5) then takes the form:

$$\frac{1}{r} h_r + \dot{h}_r + \frac{\alpha}{r} \cdot h_\phi + \chi h_z = 0 \quad (16a)$$

(here and below, dots denote derivatives with respect to r). Next, the resulting system of differential equations is solved. As a result, the solution takes the form:

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}, \quad (17)$$

$$\chi = \frac{\omega}{c} \sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (18)$$

$$e_z = Mr^{-\alpha}, \quad (19)$$

$$e_r = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\chi r} + \frac{\chi r}{\alpha} \right) e_z, \quad (20)$$

$$e_\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\chi r} - \frac{\chi r}{\alpha} \right) e_z, \quad (21)$$

$$h_r = ke_r, \quad (22)$$

$$h_\varphi = -ke_\varphi, \quad (23)$$

$$h_z = -ke_z, \quad (24)$$

where, in turn, the coefficients α , M are calculated depending on the longitudinal strength and the active power transmitted. It should be noted that this solution cannot be obtained in vector form. Thus, the beauty of the mathematical notation slowed down the process of obtaining a physically acceptable solution.

3. Solution of Maxwell's equations for vacuum in the absence of longitudinal strengths

In this case, instead of equations (2.17-2.24), the following equations are used:

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\chi = \frac{\omega}{c} \sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (2)$$

$$e_z = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$e_r = e_\varphi = Mr^{\alpha-1}, \quad (4)$$

$$h_r = -ke_r, \quad (5)$$

$$h_\varphi = ke_r, \quad (6)$$

$$h_z = 0. \quad (7)$$

4. Vector potential

Consider the vector potential A in electrodynamics, which satisfies the equation

$$\mu \cdot H = \text{rot}(A). \quad (1)$$

In the cylindrical coordinate system r, φ, z this equation has the form:

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial A_z}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{\partial A_\varphi}{\partial z} = \mu H_r, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial A_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial A_z}{\partial r} = \mu H_\varphi, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{A_\varphi}{r} + \frac{\partial A_\varphi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial A_r}{\partial \varphi} = \mu H_z. \quad (4)$$

where A_r, A_φ, A_z are components of the vector potential.

Maxwell's equations have a unique solution under the given conditions and, therefore, the vector H is known under the given conditions. The existence of a vector A compatible with the obtained H must be proved, not declared. But, since any H can be obtained in the solution of Maxwell's equations, then for the existence of the vector A , equations (1-3) must always have a solution for known H . Obviously, this requirement is not feasible! Next, we will consider this issue in more detail.

If the solution of Maxwell's equations has the form (2.9-2.16), then the vector potential has the form:

$$A_r = a_r(r) \cos, \quad (5)$$

$$A_\varphi = a_\varphi(r) \sin, \quad (6)$$

$$A_z = a_z(r) \sin. \quad (7)$$

Substituting (5-7, 2.9-2.11) into equations (2-3), we find:

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot a_z(r) \alpha - a_\varphi(r) \chi - \mu h_r(r) = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$-a_r(r) \chi - \dot{a}_z(r) - \mu h_\varphi(r) = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{a_\varphi(r)}{r} + \dot{a}_\varphi(r) + \frac{a_r(r)}{r} \cdot \alpha - \mu h_z(r) = 0. \quad (10)$$

The system of equations (8-10) determines the coefficients a depending on the known coefficients h .

Appendix 1 shows that in the general case, when all three coefficients h are given, i.e. under the existence of longitudinal strengths in vacuum, this system (8-10) has no solution. A similar conclusion can be drawn for other solutions of the system of Maxwell equations in technical devices. Thus, in the general case, the definition of a vector potential contradicts Maxwell's equations.

In the case when $h_z = 0$, i.e. in the absence of longitudinal strengths, the system of equations (8-10) takes the following form:

$$-a_\varphi(r) \chi - \mu h_r(r) = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$-a_r(r) \chi - \mu h_\varphi(r) = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{a_\varphi(r)}{r} + \dot{a}_\varphi(r) + \frac{a_r(r)}{r} \cdot \alpha = 0. \quad (13)$$

Appendix 2 shows that this system of equations has the following solution:

$$A = \frac{\mu}{\chi} H. \quad (14)$$

or, taking into account (3.2),

$$A = \frac{c}{\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\varepsilon}} H. \quad (15)$$

Thus, in this particular case, the existence of a vector potential follows directly from the system of Maxwell's equations and does not have

to be confirmed by any gauge conditions. But in the general case, the existence of a vector potential contradicts Maxwell's equations, i.e. in general, the vector potential does not exist.

Indeed, the existence of a gauge invariance condition, which can be fulfilled in many ways, introduces arbitrariness into physics that contradicts the very spirit of classical physics. With this approach, any author can construct physics without evidence at his own discretion. Unfortunately, this opportunity shamelessly used by many. In addition, the vector potential has become an obligatory attribute of any scientific article on electrodynamics, and if sometimes it is used to demonstrate the high scientific level of the author, then in other cases only the vector potential allows you to get the result the author needs. One false theory leads to many miraculous fairy tale results.

There is, however, one case - an electromagnetic wave without longitudinal strengths. In this case, the existence of the vector potential does not require additional justification. But the vector potential itself becomes proportional to the magnetic strength vector.

Attachment 1

Consider the solution of the system of equations (4.8-4.10):

$$\frac{\alpha}{r} a_z - a_\varphi \chi - \mu h_r = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$-\dot{a}_z - a_r \chi - \mu h_\varphi = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} a_\varphi + \dot{a}_\varphi + \frac{\alpha}{r} a_r - \mu h_z = 0. \quad (3)$$

From (2) we find:

$$a_r = -\frac{1}{\chi} (\dot{a}_z + \mu h_\varphi). \quad (4)$$

Combining (3, 4), we find:

$$\frac{1}{r} a_\varphi + \dot{a}_\varphi - \frac{\alpha}{r\chi} \dot{a}_z - \frac{\alpha}{r\chi} \mu h_\varphi - \mu h_z = 0. \quad (5)$$

From (1) we find:

$$a_z = \frac{r}{\alpha} (a_\varphi \chi + \mu h_r), \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{a}_z = \frac{1}{\alpha} (a_\varphi \chi - \mu h_r) + \frac{r}{\alpha} \dot{a}_\varphi \chi, \quad (7)$$

From (5, 7) we find:

$$\frac{1}{r} a_\varphi + \dot{a}_\varphi - \frac{\alpha}{r\chi} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} (a_\varphi \chi - \mu h_r) + \frac{r}{\alpha} \dot{a}_\varphi \chi \right) - \mu \left(\frac{\alpha}{r\chi} h_\varphi + h_z \right) = 0$$

or

$$\frac{1}{r\chi} h_r - \frac{\alpha}{r\chi} h_\varphi - h_z = 0. \quad (8)$$

This condition must be met in order for the system of equations (1-3) to have a solution. But equations (1-3) contradicts condition (2.16a), which is a consequence of the equation $\text{div}(H) = 0$. Therefore, the system of equations (1-3) is not compatible with the given solution of the system of Maxwell's equations.

Attachment 2

Consider the solution of the system of equations (4.11-4.13):

$$-a_\varphi(r)\chi - \mu h_r(r) = 0, \tag{1}$$

$$-a_r(r)\chi - \mu h_\varphi(r) = 0, \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{a_\varphi(r)}{r} + \dot{a}_\varphi(r) + \frac{a_r(r)}{r} \cdot \alpha = 0. \tag{3}$$

From (3.4-3.6) we find:

$$h_\varphi = -h_r = kMr^{\alpha-1}. \tag{4}$$

From (1, 2, 4) we find:

$$a_\varphi = \frac{\mu}{\chi} h_\varphi = \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^{\alpha-1}, \tag{5}$$

$$a_r = \frac{\mu}{\chi} h_r = -\frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^{\alpha-1}, \tag{6}$$

Substituting (5, 6) into (3), we get:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^{\alpha-1} + (\alpha - 1) \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^{\alpha-2} - \frac{\alpha}{r} \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^{\alpha-1} =$$

or

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^\alpha + (\alpha - 1) \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^\alpha - \frac{\alpha}{r^2} \frac{\mu}{\chi} kMr^\alpha = 0$$

or

$$1 + (\alpha - 1) - \alpha = 0$$

or

$$0 = 0.$$

Thus, the solution of the system of equations (1-3) has the form (5, 6) or

$$A = \frac{\mu}{\chi} H. \tag{7}$$

References

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